

Computer-supported diagnosis for endotension cases in endovascular aortic aneurysm repair evolution

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Abstract.

An abdominal aortic aneurysm (AAA) is a localized abnormal enlargement of the abdominal aorta with fatal consequences if not treated on time. The *Endovascular Aneurysm Repair* (EVAR) is a minimal invasive therapy that reduces recovery times and improves survival rates in AAA cases. Nevertheless, post-operation difficulties can appear influencing the evolution of treatment. The objective of this work is to develop a pilot computer-supported diagnosis system for an automated characterization of EVAR progression from CTA images. The system is based on the extraction of texture features from post-EVAR thrombus aneurysm samples and on posterior classification. Three conventional texture-analysis methods, namely the gray level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM), the gray level run length matrix (GLRLM), the gray level difference method (GLDM), and a new method proposed by the authors, the run length matrix of local co-occurrence matrices (RLMLCM), were applied to each sample. Several classification schemes were experimentally evaluated. The ensembles of a k-nearest neighbor (k-NN), a multilayer perceptron neural network (MLP-NN), and a support vector machine (SVM) classifier fed with a reduced version of texture features resulted in a better performance ($A_z = 94.35 \pm 0.30$), as compared to the classification performance of the other alternatives.

Keywords— Aneurysm, EVAR, endotension, texture features, ensembles of classifiers.

1 Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases are one of the most important causes of death in western countries and among them, abdominal aortic aneurysm (AAA) occupies an important place. Endovascular grafting of abdominal aortic is a modern minimally invasive treatment which yields good results and more rapid time recovery than classical open surgery [1],[2]. In the Endovascular Aneurysm Repair (EVAR) treatment, an stent graft is deployed inside the aneurysm cavity by an image-guided procedure. When successful, the endovascular stent graft diminishes the pressure inside the aneurysm reducing the risk of rupture. However, in a mid-long term perspective complications such as stent displacement or deformation can provoke leaks inside the aneurysm sac (endoleaks). These endoleaks may stop the exclusion of the aneurysm sac from the vascular pressure, what again increases the risk of rupture. To prevent further complications after EVAR, periodic follow-up scans of the prosthesis behavior are necessary. Nowadays, contrast enhanced computed tomographic angiography (CTA) is one of the most commonly used examinations for patients' follow-up periods. In practice, post operation analysis is quite laborious as it involves manual measurement of physical parameters of the aneurysm. At present, the maximum AAA diameter remains the most widespread criteria for the assessment of aneurysm evolution after EVAR treatment [3],[4]. According to these measurements, the evolution of the aneurysm can be split up into favorable and unfavorable. In favorable evolution, a reduction of the diameter of the aneurysm sac is observed, meaning that the aneurysm has been correctly excluded from the bloodstream. In unfavorable evolution, a decrease in aneurysm diameter is not produced due to the existence of leakages (endoleaks) allowing the persistence of blood flow within the aneurysm sac. From general clinical criteria, endoleaks are classified into type I, II, III, IV and V, depending on the source of the leakage [5]. Type I, II, III and IV need the existence of a visual evidence of the endoleak for being classified, by contrary in type V endoleaks (endotension) the reduction of pressure load inside the aneurysm sac is not produced and there is not a direct radiologic evidence of a leakage. Type V endoleaks are the most uncertain situations as the reduction of pressure load inside the aneurysm sac is not produced and there is not a direct radiologic evidence of a leakage. Even today the cause for this behavior remains a source of controversy and there is not a clear consensus on treatment guidelines [6],[7]. In these particular cases would be especially important to obtain more information about the evolution experimented inside the aneurysm cavity.

According to previous studies [8-10] texture of mass thrombus in favorable shrinking aneurysms differs from unfavorable expanding ones. In our approach, we extend the texture analysis to endotension cases in order to classify them into favourable evolution (a stabilized intrasac pressure) or unfavourable evolution (a recurrent increase of intrasac pressure). Our hypothesis is that shrinking aneurysm processes are related to coagulation and formation of thrombus or high-molecular-weight products, while expansion aneurysm mechanisms (intermittently leaks, local hyperfibrinolysis, or ultrafiltration through the graft), produce a liquefaction of intra-sac thrombus. From this point of view, intra-sac material in favorable aneurysm evolution could show textural differences from unfavorable evolution cases, even if there is no radiographic evidence of endoleaks.

At present, direct catheter pressure measurement is the most common technique for the intra-aneurysm sac pressure assessment. The proposed method may offer some benefits as compared to direct measurement, such as the elimination of risks of sac puncture and the reduction of radiation exposure or contrast-induced nephrotoxicity. Furthermore, the complementary information obtained by texture analysis might be clinically important as the strategy for endotension management is not unequivocal. A more complete assessment of endotension progression would be useful in re-defining patients' management, particularly if open surgical conversion is considered. With this idea in mind, we propose a computer assisted diagnosis (CAD) system based on texture analysis to help clinicians to determine the evolution of endotension aneurysm cases.

Fig. 1. CTA contrast enhanced images of an EVAR endotension case. (a) 1 year after treatment. (b) 2 years after treatment. (c) 3 years after treatment. White arrow points aneurysm sac in all scans. The absence of endoleaks and the no reduction of aneurysm cavity can be observed.

In recent years, many efforts have been put into the developing of Computer -Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems based on image processing methods. The principal motivation for the research on this kind of systems has been to assist the clinicians on the analysis of medical images, [11]. In many occasions this analysis implies the detection or measurement of subtle differences, usually difficult to appreciate by visual inspection even for experienced radiologist. CAD systems have been successfully utilized in a wide range of medical applications [12-16]. A particular field inside the image processing methods for CAD systems is the so named texture-based analysis. This analysis studies, not only the variation of the pixel intensity values along the image but also the possible spatial arrangement of them, and the more or less periodic repetition of such arrangement (primitives). From this point of view texture analysis can help on the functional characterization of different kind of organs, tissues, etc, at the evolution of disease. The textures features obtained from the analysis can be fed as inputs for a deterministic or probabilistic classifier, which assign each sample with its specific class.

Textures analysis methods can generally be classified into three categories: statistical methods, model based methods, and structural methods [17]. In our approach we have focused on the application of statistical texture methods, specifically, on spatial domain statistical techniques as the Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) [18], the Gray Level Run Length Matrix (GLRLM) [19] and the Gray Level Difference Method (GLDM) [20]. These three extended methods can capture second or higher order statistics on the relation between gray values in pixel pairs or groups of pixels in order to estimate their probability-density functions. Their validity has been proved in many studies [21-26]. In the last years, multiple classifier architecture has been proposed to improve the performance of CAD systems [27],[28]. In multiple classifier systems, also called classifier ensembles (EC), an initial prediction is made by several separate classifiers and then fused into one final assessment through a combining strategy [29]. Our purpose in this study is to develop a preliminary support system based on textures analysis which provides clinicians with complementary information for a better managing of endotension cases after EVAR treatment. This would be clinically important because several techniques to treat

endotension have been described and a better assessment of endotension evolution would be useful in selecting one of them.

The paper is organized as follows: "Materials and Methods" provides with information about the acquisition of CTA images, the theoretical background on the texture analysis methods, and the definition of classifier structures in the CAD system. The methodology, the results obtained from the performance evaluation of the classifiers, and discussion about them are presented in "Results and discussion". Finally, some conclusions are given in "Conclusion" section.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Dataset

The CTA image scans used in this work were obtained by a group of 3 experienced radiologists from the Vascular Surgery Unit and Interventional Radiology Department of the Donostia Hospital. These CTA images belong to the scan studies of 15 patients with ages ranging from 60 to 89 years (median 76 years), conducted over a maximum of 5 years at 1, 6, and 12 months, and yearly thereafter. The total patient set was selected by each one of the radiologist, unaware of each other's results. Only cases with complete agreement on classification among radiologists were selected in order to generate ground-truth data sets. The criteria for favourable evolution in endotension cases were based on a stable condition of the aneurysm cavity and stabilized intrasac pressure (measured by catheter). For unfavourable evolution, the criteria were based on persistent or recurrent increase of intrasac pressure or subsequent aneurysm expansion, both in the absence of endoleaks. Pressure measurement was made 14 months after EVAR in all cases. In unfavorable evolution cases, a second pressure measurement was performed between 21 and 29 months after EVAR (25 months on average). Balanced sample sets were generated for training and testing the classifier system, resulting in a total of 19 CTA studies belonged to the "favorable endotension" class and 17 to the "unfavorable endotension" one. All the studies were taken from the abdominal area with a spatial resolution of 512×512 pixels, an in-plane 0.586 (mm/pix), 12-bit gray-level at the WW400/WL40 window and 5 mm thickness in DICOM format. In order to facilitate the manual extraction of samples a specific software application was developed (Fig 2). Square regions of interest (ROI) of 15×15 pixels were manually extracted by radiologists from aneurysm thrombus. First of all, anteriorposterior aneurysm diameter measurements were obtained from CT slices orthogonal to the aortic axis in order to determine the maximum diameter slice. Once located, ROI samples were obtained from aneurysm thrombus on maximum aneurysm diameter slice, and on contiguous ± 5 mm separated slices. A total set of 74 ROIs, 38 of them corresponded to the "favorable evolution" group and 36 to the "unfavorable" one. Texture algorithms, CAD architectures and final specific application have been implemented in custom-made MATLAB source code (The MathWorks, Inc., Natick, MA).

2.2 Texture Analysis - Feature Extraction

2.2.1 Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM)

The gray level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM) [18] is an estimation of a second order joint conditional probability density function $f(i,j | d, \theta)$. This function characterizes the spatial interrelationships of the gray values in an image. The values of the co-occurrence matrix elements represent the probability of going from grey level i to grey level j given that they are separated by the distance d and the direction is given by the angle θ (usually $\theta = 0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ, \text{ and } 135^\circ$). For computing this probability the image is scanned in direction θ and the co-occurrences accumulated in the GLCM. GLCM features are extracted for primitive template matrix in the directions $0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ, \text{ and } 135^\circ$, and in some cases, averaging is done to make them direction invariant. It is a common practice to use symmetric matrices in which the co-occurrences in opposite directions are combined, so practically 8 directions are considered ($\theta = 0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ, 135^\circ, 180^\circ, 225^\circ, 270^\circ, \text{ and } 315^\circ$).

In the present application, GLCM features have been calculated from symmetrical matrices at distance 1 due to the reduced size of the aneurysm samples. Initially, the assumption of an isotropic texture distribution inside the aneurysm sac was considered, consequently averaging over the four angular directions was computed. To reduce the influence of random noise on texture features, the number of gray levels was reduced to 16 prior to the accumulation of the matrix. From GLCM matrix a set of features are obtained to classify the kind of texture analyzed. In this study, 13 features have been evaluated: Energy, correlation, inertia, entropy, inverse difference moment, sum average, sum variance, sum entropy, difference average, difference variance, difference entropy and two information measures of correlation.

Fig. 2. Software application for sample extraction.

2.2.2 Gray Level Run Length Matrix (GLRLM)

The gray level run length matrix (GLRLM) [19] higher order statistical texture information. For a given image, a run length matrix is a two-dimensional matrix in which each element $p(i, j / \theta)$ represents the total number of runs with pixels of gray value i and run length j in a certain direction θ . The number of gray levels in the image is usually reduced by re-quantization before the accumulation of the matrix. Averaging over the four angular directions was computed and the number of gray levels has been kept in 16, equal than in the GLCM method in order to make both methods comparable. Various textures features can then be extracted from the run length matrix. In our case the following 11 features have been calculated: short run emphasis, long run emphasis, gray-level non-uniformity, run length non-uniformity, run percentage, low gray-level run emphasis, high gray-level run emphasis, short run low gray-level emphasis, short run high gray-level emphasis, long run low gray-level emphasis, and long run high gray-level emphasis.

2.2.3 Gray Level Difference Method (GLDM)

The Gray Level Difference method (GLDM) [20] is based on the occurrence of two pixels which have a given absolute difference in gray level and which are separated by a specific displacement δ , estimated by the probability-density function $D(i / \delta)$. In this analysis, four possible forms of the vector δ will be considered: $(0, d)$, $(-d, d)$, $(d, 0)$, and $(d, -d)$ where d is the intersample spacing distance. Due to the reduced size of the aneurysm samples, d distance was considered equal to 1. Five textural features are measured from $D(i | \delta)$: contrast, angular second moment, entropy, mean, and inverse difference moment. As with the GLCM method, the assumption of an isotropic texture distribution inside the aneurysm sac was considered, consequently averaging over the four angular directions was computed.

2.2.4 Run Length Matrix of Local Co-occurrence Matrices (RLMLCM)

In the proposed method, the principal motivation has been to combine in a single process global and local texture information. Local or global feature extraction has been widely used in texture classification. Local features, have the drawback of losing global spatial information, while global features do not preserve little local texture information. This method offers an alternative hybrid scheme, where global features are obtained from maps of local texture matrix. Based on the work of Sridhar, *et al.* [30], local texture information is obtained at a pixel-level. Texture values were assigned to a pixel by using a window centered about that pixel. In order to capture the texture information within the window, a two-dimensional co-occurrence matrix is calculated. Once the local co-occurrence matrix is calculated around each pixel, descriptors measuring different properties of the local joint conditional probability density function $f_1(i_1, j_1 | d_1, \theta_1)$ are obtained. In this approach, we suggest to use features directly related to the local GLCM probability matrix, such as average value, standard deviation, or coefficient of variation, instead of extracting features by mean of *ad hoc* weight functions. Due to the reduced size of the aneurysm samples, a 5×5 window size and an inter-pixel d_1 distance equal to 1 were considered. The result of the process is a texture map with local texture information. Subsequently, the GLRLM method is applied on the obtained texture map in order to investigate the space distribution of local texture matrices. Averaging over the four angular directions ($\theta_1 = 0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ$, and 135°) was computed and quantization levels were kept in 16 on local and global matrices. The following 11 features have been calculated from RLMLCM matrix: short run emphasis, long run emphasis, gray-level non-uniformity, run length non-uniformity, run percentage, low gray-level run

emphasis, high gray-level run emphasis, short run low gray-level emphasis, short run high gray-level emphasis, long run low gray-level emphasis, and long run high gray-level emphasis.

2.3 Feature Selection

Two methods were employed for the feature selection process: one based on the statistical estimation of p value through Student t test and the other one by observing the change in classification efficiency through a sequential forward selection (SFS) algorithm [31]. In the last case, the SFS method has been based on Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) classifier. The optimal features selected by the combination of both methods were: energy, entropy, inverse difference moment, sum average from GLCM features, long run emphasis, run length non-uniformity from GLRLM features, angular second moment from GLDM features, and long run emphasis, gray-level non-uniformity, run length non-uniformity, long run low gray-level emphasis, long run high gray-level emphasis from RLMLCM features.

2.4 Classification

Three different computer-aided diagnosis systems (Fig 3), based on various strategies and types of classifiers were developed for comparative purposes. The first one, CAD1 (Fig 3a), consisted of an ensembles of four SVMs, each one using as input one of the four texture features vector types. A support vector machine with 13 inputs for GLCM method, one with 11 inputs for GLRLM method, one with 5 inputs for GLDM method, and finally another one with 11 inputs for RLMLCM method were implemented. The second classification alternative, CAD2 (Fig 3b) comprised three different primary classifiers, namely a k -nearest neighbor, a multilayer perceptron neural network, and a support vector machine, each one fed with the combination of the four texture feature sets. The third classification scheme, CAD3 (Fig 3c) applies the features obtained by the feature selection process to the same ensembles of classifiers of CAD2 architecture.

The final decision of all the CAD systems is generated by combining the diagnostic outputs of individual classifiers through a majority voting scheme [32]. This alternative produces a decision when at least more than half of the classifiers agree on it. The classification outputs from each classifier are combined to produce the final decision following the majority vote rule that satisfies:

$$V_n(x) = \sum_{i=1}^N d_{n,i}(x) \quad (1)$$

where x is the unknown input vector, $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ is the number of classifiers involved in the majority vote scheme, n is one of the classes, $d_{n,i}$ is the binary decision value: 1 in case i -th classifier classified input vector as class n and zero otherwise, V_n is the number of classifiers that classified input vector x as class n . The output class n which maximizes V_n is selected for prediction.

2.4.1 Support Vector Machine classifier

Support vector machine classifier is a powerful machine learning tool which generalizes well to a wide range of real-world applications, [33-35]. The basic idea of SVM classifier is to determine a separating hyperplane that distinguishes between two classes. Given a set of labeled training data, the input data are transformed into high-dimensional feature space with the use of kernel functions, so that the transformed data becomes more separable compared to the original ones. The SVM attempts to minimize a bound on the generalization error and therefore it tends to perform well when applied to data outside the training set. Lots of variety kernels can be employed for mapping input data but some of the most frequently used kernel functions are Gaussian, Polynomial and Sigmoid kernels. In this study, the Gaussian radial basis function (RBF) kernel was utilized because of its good results in many practical applications. The function kernel is defined as follows:

$$K_{RBF}(x_i, x_j) = \exp\left(-\frac{\|x_i - x_j\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (2)$$

where vector $x \in R^n$ denotes a new sample to be classified, scalar y denotes its class label and $\sigma > 0$ is a constant that defines the kernel width. The discriminant function of the SVM classifier for binary classification problems is

$$d(x) = \text{sign}\left(\sum \alpha_i y_i K_{RBF}(x, x_i) + b\right) \quad (3)$$

where x_i is the training data belonging to either class $y_i \in \{+1, -1\}$, and α_i and b are weight coefficients.

All the textural features were normalized by the sample mean and standard deviation of the data set before being fed to the SVMs. In order to determine the optimal SVMs parameters (the regularization parameter C and the width of kernel function $\gamma = 1/2\sigma$) a preliminary trial error process followed by a grid-search based on the best 10-fold cross-validation accuracy were applied. The optimal accuracy values obtained by 10-fold cross-validation for parameters C and γ in all the SVMs are shown in Table 1:

Table 1. Optimal accuracy values obtained by 10-fold cross-validation for parameters C and γ .

Classifier	C	Parameter γ	Accuracy (%)
SVM-GLCM	4.7	10.2	83.93± 0.43
SVM-GLRLM	4.3	9.6	78.28 ± 0.63
SVM-GLDM	2,8	5.3	80.11 ± 0.51
SVM-RLMLCM	5.2	10.7	86.67± 0.42
CAD2-SVM	7.3	13.4	88.45 ± 0.56
CAD3-SVM	9.1	12.7	91.66 ± 0.52

2.4.2 Multilayer Perceptron Neural Network classifier

Neural network has been widely applied to medical decision applications because of its predictive ability and robust performance. The type of neural network employed in this research has been a multilayer perceptron neural network [36], [37]. The structure for this neural network consisted of an input layer with a number of input neurons equal to the number of features of the used set, one hidden layer with a variable number of neurons, and an output layer with one neuron. A nonlinear sigmoid function with zero and one saturation values is used as the activation function for each neuron, both the hidden layer and the output layer. All the textural features were normalized by the sample mean and standard deviation of the data set before being fed to the neural network. The backpropagation algorithm with adaptive learning rate and momentum [36] was used for neural networks training. In order to find the appropriate number of hidden neurons, and the initial values for the learning rate and momentum adaption algorithm, a trial-and-error process was applied for each neural network in the CAD architecture. To evaluate the network performance during the training and testing process, the criterion was the mean square error given in Eq. (4)

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (o_i - t_i)^2 \quad (4)$$

where o_i and t_i are the output value and the target value for the i th input pattern, respectively, and N is the total number of training patterns. The training process is stopped when the MSE error no decreases for a significant number of iterations or when it starts increasing.

2.4.3 K-Nearest Neighbor classifier

The k -nearest neighbor (k -NN) classifier [38] is a very popular statistical classifier because of its simplicity and its effectiveness in many cases. This classifier implements an effective non-parametric classification approach that does not require the prior knowledge of patterns distributions. The specific algorithm classifies regarding the assignment of an unknown pattern to a class relying on a distance function between patterns. In particular, an unknown pattern is assigned the label of the class in which the most nearest training patterns (neighbors) belong. In the present study, the Euclidean distance was used as the metric of proximity between patterns. Considering the r -dimensional feature space, the Euclidean distance d_E between the unknown pattern vector \mathbf{x} and a training pattern vector \mathbf{y} is given by (5):

$$d_E = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^r (x_i - y_i)^2} \quad (5)$$

Data were normalized to zero mean and standard deviation equal to one and the number of k -neighbors for the k -NN classifiers in CAD schemes were experimentally determined.

Fig. 3. Implemented CAD schemes, (a) CAD1, (b) CAD2 and (c) CAD3

3 Results and discussion

In order to evaluate the potential of texture analysis based CAD systems to classify between the two types of endotension aneurysm evolution the development and validation of the different classifiers have been based on the 10-fold cross validation method. Samples from the same patient have been kept together in either train or test set in order to avoid biased results. To improve the evaluation of performance of the feature sets, the 10-fold cross validation was repeated 6 times, averaging the results. The averages of accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity for all the trials were used as an estimate of the performance of each classifier. Table 2 shows the accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity values (mean \pm standard deviation) estimated by cross validation of the testing sets for primary classifiers and CAD1 scheme.

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation values for classification accuracy, sensitivity and specificity (in %) of the testing sets for primary classifiers and CAD1 architecture

Classifier	Accuracy (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)
GLCM	83.93± 0.43	85.73± 0.44	79.21± 0.41
GLRLM	78.28 ± 0.63	80.10 ± 0.51	75.03 ± 0.63
GLDM	80.11 ± 0.51	82.38 ± 0.47	76.16 ± 0.43
RLMLCM	86.67± 0.42	88.02± 0.38	83.27± 0.45
CAD1	89.74 ± 0.33	90.62 ± 0.29	85.48 ± 0.37

From the Table 2 it is shown that the ensembles of SVM classifiers architecture (CAD1) yielded to a better performance (89.74 ± 0.33) than the RLMLCM (86.67 ± 0.42), GLCM (83.93 ± 0.43), GLDM (80.11 ± 0.51), and GLRLM (78.28 ± 0.63) primary classifiers.

The classification results estimated by cross validation of the testing sets for CAD2, CAD3, and their respective individual classifiers are depicted in Table 3.

Table 3. Mean and standard deviation values for classification accuracy, sensitivity and specificity (in %) of the testing sets for primary classifiers and CAD2 and CAD3 architectures.

Classifier	Accuracy (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)
k-NN	72.86 ± 0.55	76.13 ± 0.56	67.84 ± 0.61
MLP	86.78 ± 0.48	87.77 ± 0.51	82.03 ± 0.48
SVM	88.45 ± 0.56	90.06 ± 0.51	86.33 ± 0.57
CAD2	92.41 ± 0.42	92.57 ± 0.39	88.62 ± 0.47
k-NN	73.92 ± 0.47	77.28 ± 0.51	69.61 ± 0.41
MLP	88.26 ± 0.41	90.19 ± 0.53	84.23 ± 0.43
SVM	89.66 ± 0.52	91.29 ± 0.49	87.76 ± 0.54
CAD3	94.35 ± 0.30	95.16 ± 0.33	91.47 ± 0.37

From Table 3, it can be observed that the best classification performance was achieved by CAD3 with an accuracy of 94.35 ± 0.30 , followed by the CAD2 with 92.41 ± 0.42 , and the SVM with 91.66 ± 0.52 , the MLP with 88.26 ± 0.41 , and the k-NN classifier with 73.92 ± 0.47 , after the feature selection process. It is notable that the feature selection module in CAD3 improves slightly the performance of CAD2 with less computational cost. According to the results from Table 2 and 3, it is showed that the best accuracy among all the alternatives is obtained by CAD3 scheme (94.35 ± 0.30) using the reduced feature set, followed by CAD2 (92.41 ± 0.42) and CAD1 (89.74 ± 0.33) architectures. For comparative purposes, Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve (Fig 4) and area under the ROC curve (A_z) were also used as a measure of the classification performance. Table 4 presents the A_z values (mean ± standard deviation) calculated for training and testing feature sets using the 10-fold cross validation for the CAD1, CAD2, and CAD3 schemes.

Table 4. Az values (mean \pm standard deviation) calculated for training and testing sets using the 10-fold cross validation for CAD1, CAD2, and CAD3 schemes.

Classifier	Az mean training	Az mean testing
CAD1	0.921 \pm 0.022	0.907 \pm 0.032
CAD2	0.941 \pm 0.017	0.936 \pm 0.026
CAD3	0.963 \pm 0.014	0.957 \pm 0.020

The achieved values show that the greatest area under the ROC curve, and consequently the best performance of classifiers is obtained again by CAD3 ($A_z = 0.957 \pm 0.020$) followed by CAD2 ($A_z = 0.936 \pm 0.026$), and CAD1 ($A_z = 0.907 \pm 0.032$) confirming the previous results.

Fig. 4. ROC curves for the CAD1, CAD2, and CAD3 architectures.

From the results in Table 2, 3 and 4, CAD3 can be considered as the most appropriate CAD architecture for discriminating the endotension aneurysm evolution. These results indicate that classifier combination strategies significantly enhance accuracy, sensitivity and specificity compared to single classifiers. The better performance of these architectures can be explained on the basis of an ensemble of classifiers allows exploitation of complementary information content in the different input sets and also because multiple classifier systems generalize better than single ones [18]. At the same time, it is illustrated that the combination of textural features from different methods may improve the classification accuracy and perform better than individual ones. It is worth noting that the RLMCM method was shown to be superior to conventional texture-analysis methods, what can make this new technique an interesting option in specific texture analysis.

4 Conclusions

In the present work, we have studied the capability of CAD systems based on textures analysis for discriminating the evolution of abdominal aortic aneurysm complicated by endotension after EVAR procedure. For this purpose, texture parameters have been extracted from ROI samples by three classical methods, GLCM, GRLM, GLDM and a new method proposed by the authors: the run length matrix of local co-occurrence matrices (RLLCM).

At the same time, different classification strategies have been proposed for the implementation of the CAD system. The best performing architecture consisted of an ensemble of a k-nearest neighbor, a multilayer perceptron NN, and a support vector machine, each one fed with an input subset obtained after appropriate feature selection of the total feature set. The final decision of the CAD system is generated by combining the diagnostic outputs of individual classifiers through a majority voting scheme. The mean classification accuracy achieved by the system after 10-fold cross validation of the testing sets was equal to 94.35 ± 0.30 .

Although the results are encouraging, the proposed CAD system should be considered as preliminary, taking into account the limited number of patients. Further investigations will be needed to assess the potential of the system as a clinical tool for assisting physicians in the characterization of aneurysm endotension cases after EVAR treatment. Additionally, the study provides a proper baseline to work more deeply on endotension cases. In these situations, a more complete assessment of EVAR progression is clinically important due to the existence of different management strategies.

In conclusion, the results indicate that the proposed CAD system might provide a valuable “second opinion” tool for radiologists in the diagnosis of endotension endovascular aortic aneurysm repair evolution.

5 Conflict of interest statement

None declared.

6 References

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